

Modelling cetacean habitats in the Eastern Caribbean : a study combining data from multiple sources

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Abstract

Cetaceans play a key role in the balance of the marine ecosystem. However, they are subject to numerous environmental and anthropogenic pressures. Understanding and mapping their distribution can contribute to their conservation. The Agoa Sanctuary in the Eastern Caribbean is home to over 35% of all cetacean species. However, modelling of their distribution in this marine protected area has never been undertaken.

This study aimed to address this gap by applying Species Distribution Models (SDM) to presence-only data collected between 2008 and 2022 from multiple sources, including boat and aerial surveys, focal studies and opportunistic data. Pseudo-absences were sampled on surveyed locations following a sampling weight which changed according to data source. Multiple SDM models were combined into ensemble models to generate predictive distribution maps. The distribution was modelled for 7 species: the humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*), the sperm whale (*Physeter macrocephalus*), the bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*), the false killer whale (*Pseudorca crassidens*), the pantropical spotted dolphin (*Stenella attenuata*), the Fraser's dolphin (*Lagenodelphis hosei*), and the short-finned pilot whale (*Globicephala macrorhynchus*). When the number of sightings allowed it, three separate time periods were considered: the dry season (December-May), the wet season (June-November), and the full-year (both seasons combined).

Depth, biomass of the highly migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton, photosynthetic radiation and variation in sea surface height were consistently identified as the most explanatory variables. For all species, the most favourable habitats were predicted on the leeward coasts, to the west of the Caribbean islands. The favourable habitats of the pantropical spotted dolphin and sperm whale were more extensive in the dry season than in the wet season. The opposite was observed for the bottlenose dolphin.

The modelling process was optimized by incorporating state-of-the-art computational methods with a complex and heterogeneous dataset. This work will allow improving cetacean management in the area by combining the distribution maps with maritime traffic, a major pressure leading to collisions and noise disturbance. This work could also be carried out using multi-species modelling, to identify interactions between species and map the habitats of other, less commonly observed species.

Keywords: cetaceans; species distribution models; opportunistic data; standardized data; pseudo-absence generation

Introduction

Marine ecosystems provide multiple services. In particular, they help regulate the impacts of climate change by acting as carbon sinks and an oxygen sources (Bearzi, 2012; Pershing et al., 2010). Cetaceans, as keystone species, maintain the balance of these ecosystems (Albouy et al., 2020). In conservation biology, cetaceans are also referred to as umbrella species, as their protection enables the protection of other species in the marine ecosystem (Bearzi, 2012). However, these species are subject to multiple pressures from human activities such as climate change, fishing, tourism or maritime traffic (Farmer et al., 2022; Madon et al., 2022). Mapping favorable habitats and understanding them through the identification of explanatory variables helps improving species conservation strategies (Araújo, 2009; Enriquez-Urzelai et al., 2019). Species Distribution Modeling (SDM) is commonly used for this purpose.

Distribution modeling is a major area of research in conservation biology. Modeling distribution means understanding the ecological niche, defined as a hyper-volume with n-dimensions, each corresponding to a state of the environment that would allow a species to exist indefinitely (Soberón and Arroyo-Peña, 2017). The fundamental niche represents the conditions that allow the species to live in the absence of interactions. The realized niche is the fundamental niche reduced by competitive and predatory interactions or extended by beneficial interactions such as symbiosis or mutualism (Gvoždík, 2018; Soberón and Arroyo-Peña, 2017). Correlative modelling highlights the realized niche, as interactions between species are implicitly integrated by the occurrence data (Dormann, Schymanski, et al., 2012). This approach builds statistical relationships between presence-only or presence-absence data and environmental data. The statistical links are fixed in time and space, and are highly dependent on the observed data and tested variables (Dormann, Schymanski, et al., 2012). Careful selection of variables consistent with the biology of species and limitation of extrapolation in non-surveyed areas help reduce this dependency (Mannocci et al., 2017). Several models, called individual models, can be built using different statistical methods and different training datasets. The best models are finally combined to produce an ensemble model used for prediction. This final step provides better predictive performance than each individual model taken on its own. Ensemble models also help evaluating the agreement between individual models by calculating the coefficient of variation between individual predictions (Braunisch et al., 2013; Guisan et al., 2017).

Several distribution modelling studies have already been carried out on cetacean species around the world. The work of Virgili, Hedon, et al. (2021) conducted in the Atlantic Ocean, has shown that the sperm whale (*Physeter macrocephalus*) is present mainly at depths of around 2000m, in areas where the production of epipelagic organisms (layer from the surface to 200m depth) is greater than 0.2 g.m^{-2} and where the sea surface temperature gradient is greater than 2°C . Another study conducted in the Caribbean on dolphins of the genus *Stenella* showed that these species prefer coastal habitats (medians 4 km, 42 km, and 5 km, respectively, for *S. frontalis*, *S. attenuata*, and *S. longirostris*), with a mean chlorophyll-a concentration of, respectively, 0.64 mg.m^{-3} , 0.21 mg.m^{-3} , and 0.38 mg.m^{-3} , a variable correlated with prey presence (Barragán-Barrera et al., 2019). Other studies highlighted the importance of eddy kinetic energy (EKE) (Pardo et al., 2015), slope and sea surface temperature (SST) (Virgili, Racine, et al., 2017), as well as seafloor nature and sea surface height (SSH) (Frasier et al., 2021).

The distribution of cetaceans in the Eastern Caribbean has not been extensively studied. Yet, 35% of known cetacean species are present in these waters. The Agoa Sanctuary is a marine protected area created in 2010, dedicated to the preservation of marine mammals of the French Caribbean. It extends over the exclusive economic zone of the French Antilles (Saint-Martin, Saint-Barthélemy, Guadeloupe, Martinique), covering an area of $143,256 \text{ km}^2$ (see Fig 1). It is managed by the French Biodiversity Agency (OFB), a public entity under the administrative supervision of the French Ministries in charge of agriculture and the environment. A

few large-scale studies have been carried out in the Sanctuary : Gandilhon (2012) participated in the acquisition of sighting data, Vachon et al. (2022) showed that there were several sperm whale vocal clans in the Caribbean Haderlé (2022) suggested the existence of two morphotypes of bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*) in Guadeloupe. These studies are a first step towards understanding the distribution of species in the Agoa Sanctuary, but have not produced species distribution maps, an important tool for managing the marine area.

Since 2008, the Agoa Sanctuary has been carrying out several standardized cetacean observation surveys. Additionally, occasional surveys during dredging operations or impact studies, as well as tours by local associations and whale-watching companies, have led to the acquisition of opportunistic data. Opportunistic data are still rarely used in models mainly because of the lack of sampling design, the uncertainty associated with species identification or the bias relative to observer diversity (Giraud et al., 2016; Maes et al., 2015). However, they are often far more numerous than standardized data and therefore can provide useful information (Dalili, 2019). For instance, Giraud et al. (2016) highlighted the strength of opportunistic data, particularly for discrete species. Their use, combined with a smaller quantity of standardized data, improved the accuracy of abundance estimates. Often more widely distributed than standardized data, opportunistic data is also used to inform the species distribution in the IUCN red lists (Maes et al., 2015). Combining the two data sources remains difficult because methods for accounting for bias in opportunistic data are still being developed (Cretois et al., 2021). Our database only contained presence data whereas most species distribution models require absence data (Dormann, Schymanski, et al., 2012). We have developed a method for generating pseudo-absences, depending on the different data sources.

Our study aimed at combining multiple types of data, from standardized surveys to opportunistic sightings, to produce the first high-resolution distribution maps for cetaceans over the whole French West Indies. The method developed in this study could helpfully inform similar exercises in the Wider Caribbean Region. Moreover, the resulting prediction maps as well as the identification of variables explaining presence probability will prove useful for informing the conservation management of those species in the Agoa Sanctuary and beyond. Finally, the method to construct pseudo-absences could also be reused.

Material and methods

Study area

The study area encompassed the Agoa Sanctuary together with neighbouring islands such as Anguilla at its northern boundary, Dominica in its center and Saint Lucia as its southern boundary (see Fig 1). This choice was motivated by similar ecological issues across the entire Caribbean arc, which represents an ecological continuum for marine mammals. Additionally, the data collected outside the administrative boundaries of the Agoa Sanctuary were more scattered than the data collected near the islands within the Sanctuary. As such, these data from outside the boundaries were valuable for the modeling process.

Available data

Part of the data was collected during aerial surveys (REMMAO surveys 2008 and 2017) and during boat surveys (Agoa surveys 2012, 2013, 2014, ANBADLO 2020 survey and CARI'MAM 2021 surveys), all following a standardised transect protocol. Other data were collected during one-off studies such as dredging operations (GPMG 2015), impact studies (BIOTOPE 2015, Karubenthos 2015), census survey (Gandilhon, 2012 (Gandilhon, 2012)), telemetric monitoring (Megara 2014-2019), and through citizen science (Breach Antilles, Réserve Naturelle Saint-Martin, Megaptera 2020, OBIS - Ocean Biodiversity Information System, OMMAG - Observatoire

Figure 1. Distribution of sightings for the seven most commonly observed species in the study area, stretching from Anguilla to Saint Lucia and including the Agoa Sanctuary (administrative boundaries in blue).

des Mammifères Marins de l'Archipel Guadeloupéen) and whale watching operators. In the following, we will refer to data recorded during transect surveys as effort data and to other data as off-effort data. Only visual sightings made between December 1, 2007 and August 31, 2022, associated with GPS coordinates and for which species identification was confident, were retained for modeling. Distribution modeling was carried out for the most common species: pantropical spotted dolphin (*Stenella attenuata*, 1038 sightings), sperm whale (*Physeter macrocephalus*, 752 sightings), humpback whale (*Megaptera novaeangliae*, 742 sightings), Fraser's dolphin (*Lagenodelphis hosei*, 211 sightings), bottlenose dolphin (*Tursiops truncatus*, 211 sightings), false killer whale (*Pseudorca crassidens*, 96 sightings) and short-finned pilot whale (*Globicephala macrorhynchus*, 87 sightings) (see Fig 1). Observations were mostly concentrated near the coast and were rarer in the eastern part of the Sanctuary.

Spatio-temporal resolutions

Modeling was performed at a 0.02° resolution (approximately 2.2 km). Aggregating observations at this resolution was a good compromise between representing the environment and avoiding over-aggregation. Indeed, working with a too large grid would have resulted in a significant loss of information, as illustrated by Barragán-Barrera et al. (2019). By opting for a grid cell size of 9.2 km, these authors identified only 84 occupied cells for the pantropical spotted dolphin, despite having 1086 sightings of this species in their data. Conversely, a cell size too small would have had no ecological sense as marine mammals travel several tens of kilometers per day (Cantor et al., 2019; Cobarrubia-Russo et al., 2020; Dalla Rosa et al., 2008; Martínez-Serrano et al., 2011; Ross, 2006; Visser, 1999).

Three time periods were distinguished: the full-year from December to November (capturing the ecological year), the dry season from December to May, and the wet season from June to November. Models were built

for each time period for which at least 50 cells were occupied by the species, according to the recommendations of Guisan et al. (2017).

The distributions of the sperm whale, pantropical spotted dolphin, and bottlenose dolphin were modeled over all three time periods. The distributions of false killer whales, Fraser's dolphins, and short-finned pilot whales were modeled over the full-year and the dry season. Finally, the distribution of the humpback whales was modeled only during the dry season as they were only present in the Eastern Caribbean during period for breeding, and migrate northward to feeding areas during the wet season (Réserve Naturelle de Saint Martin, 2014, 2019).

Generation of pseudo-absences

Informing pseudo-absences from effort data and non-detection

A majority of mathematical models involved in SDMs require geolocated species absence data. However, our database only contained presence data. It was therefore necessary to artificially generate absence data, referred to as pseudo-absences (PA). The strategy for generating PA was informed by certain properties of the dataset, so that the distribution of sampling intensity of PA was similar to that of observations (Kéry et al., 2010). Two methods were combined: informing PA from the effort data of standardised surveys (Fiedler et al., 2018) and from non-detection data derived from off-effort data (Kéry et al., 2010). In the first method, effort cells along a transect followed during sampling were considered as PA when the species was not detected (Fiedler et al., 2018). In the second method, cells in which at least one other species, but not the target species, was observed were considered as PA. This method is based on the principle that the GPS coordinates of a point where any species was observed are inventory points where any unobserved species is considered absent (Kéry et al., 2010). The generation of PA was carried out separately for the three time periods, the full-year, the dry season, and the wet season (see Fig 2).

Weighting pseudo-absences according to their source

Generating pseudo-absences can be complex. It relies primarily on taking into account two sampling biases: the availability of the animal at the surface to be detected and the observer's detection ability, which also depends on weather conditions (Forcada et al., 2004; Lambert, Authier, et al., 2019). These two biases vary according to the observation methods, by boat and by plane. By plane, the observation time is very short (about 4 seconds), the covered area is larger and species that barely emerge from the water are better detected than by boat, as individuals are visible through transparency (Dorémus et al., 2020). By boat, small and dark animals are better detected and species identification is easier (Laran, Authier, Blanck, et al., 2017). Detection probabilities also differ according to species (Hammond et al., 2021). Observation distances vary according to species, which may show attraction or repulsion behaviors towards approaching boats and aerial flyovers (Hammond, 2007). Detectability also depends on the time spent at the surface: 65% to 75% of the time for small *Delphinidae* and *Globicephalinae* versus 20% for the sperm whale (Forcada et al., 2004; Gómez de Segura et al., 2006; Laran, Authier, Van Canneyt, et al., 2017). During the SCANS III survey, Hammond et al. (2021) estimated the detection probabilities on the same transect for boat and plane methods for a few species. For dolphins, pilot whales, and false killer whales, this work allowed a weight to be defined that was twice as important for pseudo-absences from aerial surveys than from boat surveys. For the humpback whale, the weighting was set to be the same for sightings collected by plane and boat. For the sperm whale, given its ecological characteristics - long dive time and discreet species (Baird et al., 2022; Laran, Authier, Van Canneyt, et al., 2017) - a weight twice as important was assigned to pseudo-absences resulting from aerial surveys. To summarize, for all species, except humpback whale, a weight of 1 was associated with boat passages and non-detections in occasional surveys and opportunistic observations, while a weight of 2 was associated with

Figure 2. Mapping off-effort and effort sightings in the dry (DS) and wet (WS) seasons (a). Maps b, c, and d show the number of passages per cell over the full-year according to the transects traveled by boat (b), by plane (c), and according to non-detections (d).

plane passages. For the humpback whale, weights were the same whatever the observation method. For each cell, the number of passages by boat, by plane, and the number of detections were counted. Sampling probability of PA cells was calculated from these weights, by summing on each source, after excluding the cells where the focal species or unidentified cetaceans at the species level had been observed.

Defining the number of pseudo-absences and the number of sets

Number of pseudo-absences was set to be identical to the number of presences for each modelled species, following the recommendations of Barbet-Massin et al. (2012). They also advised sampling 20% of the study area according to a random PA drawing strategy. Knowing that the PA were drawn in the prospected area according to informed weighting and that there were few sightings per species, a total of 10% of the cells in the prospected area was sampled. This choice led to a variable number of PA sets according to species, allowing to exceed a threshold of 1575 sampled pseudo-absence cells (*i.e.* 10% of 15750 sampled cells in the 0.02° grid) for each species. Thus, four PA sets were generated for the humpback whale, six for the pantropical spotted dolphin, seven for the sperm whale, twelve for the bottlenose dolphin, thirteen for Fraser's dolphin, and twenty-five for the false killer whale and the short-finned pilot whale.

Explanatory Variables

Downloading and preparing variables

Following a literature review on the distribution of marine mammals, 19 potentially relevant variables were selected: 5 static variables and 14 dynamic variables (see Table 1) (Barragán-Barrera et al., 2019; De Rock et al.,

Variable	Downloading source	Resolutions
Depth and slope	GEBCO, link	450 m
Sediment thickness	NOAA, link	9 km
Longitude and Latitude		
CHL and PAR	MODIS (Gohin et al., 2005), link	4,6 km, montly
SST	CMEMS, link	5 km, daily
SSH and EKE	CMEMS, link	27 km, daily
SEAPODYM variables	CMEMS (Lehodey et al., 2021), link	2 km, daily

Table 1. Static and dynamic variables downloaded from different databases at various spatial and temporal resolutions. The dynamic variables are chlorophyll a concentration (CHL); photosynthetic radiation (PAR); sea surface temperature (SST); sea surface height (SSH); eddy kinetic energy (EKE) and the 9 variables from the SEAPODYM prey model.

2019; Effrosynidis et al., 2020; Fernandez et al., 2021; Frasier et al., 2021; Mannocci et al., 2017; Martino et al., 2021; Virgili, Hedon, et al., 2021; Virgili, Racine, et al., 2017). The dynamic variables were downloaded over the period December 2007 - November 2022.

Depth was derived from the bathymetry data layer provided by GEBCO (GEneral Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans) at a resolution of 450 m. The slope was calculated from the depth layer using the `terrain` function of the raster R package (Hijmans et al., 2023). The eddy kinetic energy (EKE) was calculated from the eastward and northward sea water velocity (ESWV and NSWV) using the equation: $EKE = \frac{1}{2} \times (ESWV^2 + NSWV^2)$, obtained from the absolute dynamic topography model. SEAPODYM is an ecosystem model that simulates changes in abundance at two trophic levels, zooplankton and micronekton (Lehodey et al., 2021). The model simulates the biomass of zooplankton, epipelagic micronekton, lower mesopelagic micronekton (non-migrant, migrant and highly migrant trophic levels) and upper mesopelagic micronekton (non-migrant and migrant trophic levels). In the study area, some biomass variables had not been calculated by the model because the depth layer was nonexistent. To avoid the loss of cells due to this missing information, the value 0 was assigned to cells where a value of the epipelagic micronekton biomass was present, signifying that the SEAPODYM model had been calculated on these cells, as recommended in Virgili, Hedon, et al. (2021). The model also estimates the net primary production and the euphotic zone.

The dynamic variables measured at a daily resolution were averaged monthly. The median and the standard deviation were calculated over the full-year, the dry season and the wet season. For example, the standard deviation of a variable in the dry season was defined by the standard deviation of the monthly averages from December to May, over the 15 years of the study. The median statistic was chosen instead of the mean to represent the central tendency, and the standard deviation was chosen instead of the range to represent dispersion. In a standard machine learning strategy, models can be built using all four statistics (mean, median, standard deviation and range) to evaluate which ones are best for predicting species distribution (Effrosynidis et al., 2020). From an ecological perspective, the median better represents the central tendency of variables that are not normally distributed. The standard deviation is less sensitive to extreme values than the range. In this study, modeling was based on 15 years of observation data, so it was more relevant to exclude rare extreme events. Thus, the median and standard deviation statistics were chosen for both ecological and statistical reasons.

Finally, all variables were aggregated on the 0.02° grid using the bilinear method, from the `projectRaster` function of the raster R package (Hijmans et al., 2023). This method calculates the average of the values of the four adjacent cells, weighted by the distances between their centroids and the centroid of the target cell (Chang, 2006). Cells overlapping the contours of the study area were kept in order to avoid losing edge

information.

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Selecting Variables

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Two selection criteria were applied to the variables. The first was the correlation criterion. It is important to ensure that uncorrelated variables are used because correlations can hide the effects of relevant variables (Braunisch et al., 2013; Heikkinen et al., 2006). Moreover, this can lead to over-parameterization of the model due to information redundancy (Astruc et al., 2018; Harris et al., 2013). Dormann, Elith, et al. (2013) showed a significant effect of correlations higher than 0.7 on the construction of response curves and predictions. Thus, variables were selected according to a Spearman correlation coefficient lower than 0.7. This selection was made manually to maximize the number of common variables between time periods. The second criterion was the permutation importance index, calculated for each variable in a preliminary model, built with all the variables selected according to the first criterion. Only the 10 most explanatory variables, with the highest permutation importance index, for each species and for each period, were retained (see Table 2). This sub-selection allowed for increased computational efficiency and limited bias induced by a too high number of variables (Clavel-Henry et al., 2020; Hastie et al., 2009).

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The depth and the median of the highly migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton biomass (lowhm_med) were selected for all species and all study periods. The standard deviation of the migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton biomass (lowm_sd) was always selected, except for the humpback whale. Medians of the photosynthetic radiation (par_med) and the non-migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton biomass (low_med) were also selected for most species and time periods, as were standard deviations of the highly migrant and the migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton biomasses (lowhm_sd and lowm_sd). Other variables were retained: sediment thickness, medians of the eddy kinetic energy (eke_med), of the zooplankton biomass (zoo_med), of the sea surface height (ssh_med) and of the migrant upper mesopelagic micronekton biomass (uppm_med) as well as standard deviations of the chlorophyll a concentration (chl_sd), of the sea surface height (ssh_sd), of the migrant upper mesopelagic micronekton biomass (uppm_sd), of the non-migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton biomass (low_sd) and of the net primary production (ppn_sd) (see Table 2).

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Modeling with Biomod2

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Fitted models

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In this study, we fitted various models implemented in biomod2 version 4.2-3 (Thuiller et al., 2023): logistic regressions (GLM); generalized additive models (GAM); flexible discriminant analysis (FDA); multiple additive regression splines (MARS); artificial neural networks (ANN); classification trees (CTA); random forests (RF); boosted trees (GBM) and the Maxent-Phillips model (MAXNET). Each of these models has specific calibration parameters called hyperparameters (Hastie et al., 2009), such as the number of trees in GBM or the number of splines in GAM. In this study, interactions between variables in the GLM method were not considered. The GBM method was restricted to a maximum of 1000 trees and the GAM method to a maximum of 4 splines. Setting this parameter to 4 allowed the existence of two optima on the response curves and avoided model overfitting (Pickens et al., 2021; Wood, 2006).

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Model Evaluation

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For each species studied, the fitted individual models were evaluated by cross-validation, so the observations were divided into two samples. The training sample was used to build the model, which was then used to predict presence and absence in the test sample. A performance index was calculated to measure the agreement of the predictions with the actual presences and absences. Replicating this process reduced the effect of dataset partitioning (Carvalho et al., 2010; Chapman et al., 2019), thus increasing the robustness of

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Variable	Mnov	Pmac	Ttru	Pcra	Satt	Lhos	Gmac
slope			FY DS WS				FY DS
depth	DS	FY DS WS	FY DS WS	FY DS	FY DS WS	FY DS	FY DS
sediment		WS	WS	DS	FY DS WS		
eke_med	DS	DS WS	FY DS		DS WS	FY DS	FY DS
low_med	DS	FY DS WS	DS WS	FY DS	FY DS WS	FY DS	FY DS
lowhm_med	DS	FY DS WS	FY DS WS	FY DS	FY DS WS	FY DS	FY DS
par_med	DS	FY WS	FY DS WS	FY	FY DS WS	FY DS	FY
zoo_med				DS			
chl_sd	DS	DS		DS		DS	DS
lowhm_sd	DS	FY DS WS	FY	FY	FY DS WS	FY DS	FY DS
lowm_sd		FY DS WS	FY DS WS	FY DS	FY DS WS	FY DS	FY DS
ssh_sd	DS	FY DS WS	DS WS	FY DS	FY WS	FY	
uppm_sd		DS		FY DS	DS	FY DS	FY DS
low_sd	DS	FY DS	FY DS	FY DS	FY DS		FY DS
ppn_sd		FY	FY WS	FY			
ssh_med		FY WS	FY WS		FY WS	FY	
uppm_med	DS		DS			DS	

Table 2. Variables selected over the full-year (FY), the dry (DS) and wet (WS) seasons for humpback whales (Mnov), sperm whales (Pmac), bottlenose dolphins (Ttru), false killer whales (Pcra), pantropical spotted dolphins (Satt), Fraser’s dolphins (Lhos) and short-finned pilot whales (Gmac). The first and second blocks are associated with common variables to all three time periods, distinguishing respectively static and dynamic variables. The third block contains the remaining variables.

performance index estimates (Stone, 1974). In this study, cross-validation was repeated 10 times, according to a split of 70% for training and 30% for testing datasets (Astruc et al., 2018; Liang et al., 2018; Sousa-Guedes et al., 2020). The performance of the models was evaluated with the TSS (True Skill Statistic) criterion and considered good when TSS > 0.7 (Lyons and Kozak, 2020).

Variable importance

Variable importance measures its contribution to the construction of the model. The higher the contribution, the more determinant the variable is in predicting favorable habitats for the species. Variable importance was obtained using a permutation process repeated 5 times for each variable (Astruc et al., 2018; Liang et al., 2018; Sousa-Guedes et al., 2020). The importance indices were averaged over all cross-validation repetitions of pseudo-absence sets to obtain one importance index per variable and per modeling method. For each variable, relative importance (%) was obtained by dividing the importance index by the sum of importance indexes for all 10 variables involved in the model.

Ensemble modeling

Ensemble modeling combines the results of a selection of individuals models with high performance (Araujo and New, 2007; Guisan et al., 2017; Hao et al., 2019). Taking into account multiple models reduces the uncertainty associated with each model (Heikkinen et al., 2006; Lyons and Kozak, 2020). Ensemble models were obtained by averaging the probabilistic predictions of the models, weighted by the TSS evaluation score. The coefficient of variation can also be calculated to estimate the uncertainty between all the models used for the ensemble modeling. For each species, the ensemble models were built from highly performing models (TSS > 0.7). They were used to produce maps of favorable habitats, which were interpreted using the response curves of the most important variables and considering the coefficient of variation of the predictions.

All analyses were performed using R 4.2.3 Team (Team, 2023) and biomod2 4.2-3 (Thuiller et al., 2023).

Results

Evaluation according to TSS

The number of individual models whose TSS exceeded the threshold of 0.7 was greater than 30 for all species and all periods, allowing the construction of statistically correct ensemble models (Wisz et al., 2008). All ensemble models had TSS scores above 0.7, except the model for the bottlenose dolphin in the wet season (TSS = 0.685).

Most important variables

For both the full-year and the dry season, regardless of species, the median of the biomass from the highly migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton (lowhm_med) was always (except the model for the bottlenose dolphin during the dry season) among the most explanatory variables, with a relative importance index higher than 10% (see Table 3). Depth was the second variable common to all time periods and species, but was not systematically ranked as the most explanatory. It showed explanatory for all three time periods for the pantropical spotted dolphin and the bottlenose dolphin, with a particularly high contribution for the latter: 55% over the full-year, 40% in the dry season, and 39% in the wet season (see Table 3). It was also explanatory for the sperm whale over the full-year and the dry season, for Fraser's dolphin and the humpback whale in the dry season, and for the short-finned pilot whale over the full-year. It was never among the most important variables for the false killer whale (see Table 3). Over the full-year, the median photosynthetic radiation (par_med) was also one of the most explanatory variables for the four dolphin species. This variable was not explanatory for the sperm whale and the false killer whale (see Table 3).

Pmac - FY	Ttru - FY	Pcra - FY	Satt - FY	Lhos - FY	Gmac - FY
ssh_sd 21%	depth 55%	lowm_sd 25%	lowhm_med 23%	lowhm_med 20%	par_med 17%
depth 15%	par_med 11%	lowhm_med 20%	par_med 16%	par_med 19%	lowhm_med 16%
low_med 13%	lowhm_med 10%	ssh_sd 11%	ssh_sd 13%	lowm_sd 13%	low_med 14%
lowhm_med 13%			depth 11%	depth 10%	lowhm_sd 12%
lowm_sd 12%					uppm_sd 10%
lowm_sd 12%					depth 10%
Pmac - DS	Ttru - DS	Pcra - DS	Satt - DS	Lhos - DS	Gmac - DS
lowhm_med 39%	depth 40%	lowhm_med 46%	lowhm_med 46%	lowhm_med 34%	lowhm_med 35%
depth 15%	par_med 26%	uppm_sd 11%	low_med 13%	uppm_sd 21%	slope 14%
low_med 14%	eke_med 10%		depth 12%		uppm_sd 12%
Pmac - WS	Ttru - WS		Satt - WS		Mnov - DS
lowm_sd 43%	depth 39%		lowm_sd 29%		depth 40%
lowhm_sd 13%	par_med 18%		ssh_sd 15%		ssh_sd 18%
	lowhm_med 14%		par_med 14%		eke_med 12%
					lowhm_med 10%

Table 3. Variables ranked by their contribution to the modeling process over the full-year (FY), the dry (DS) and the wet (WS) seasons. Only variables contributing with an average contribution of at least 10% are listed (average across models with a TSS greater than 0.7). Mnov : humpback whale, Pmac : sperm whale, Ttru : bottlenose dolphin, Pcra : false killer whale, Satt : pantropical spotted dolphin, Lhos : Fraser's dolphin, Gmac : short-finned pilot whale.

Overall distribution of the seven species

Favorable habitats for the sperm whale were mainly predicted to the west of the islands. The most favorable areas, with a presence probability close to 1, were close to the coasts. The presence probability was close to 0.75 in the north-west of the study area although very few observations were made in this less surveyed area. However, the physical (depth and surface water height) and trophic (lower mesopelagic micronekton biomass) conditions of the environment were similar to those where observations were made, hence supporting this prediction. These results were also strengthened by low coefficients of variation (close to 0.04, see Fig 3).

Favorable habitats for the bottlenose dolphin over the full-year surrounded the islands and the large banks, where the depth is shallower. The areas of favorable habitat also showed one of the lowest photosynthetic radiation levels in the study area and a biomass of highly migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton close to 1.5 g.m^{-2} . These results were supported by a minimal coefficient of variation in these zones compared to the other zones of the study area (see Fig 3).

Favorable habitats for the false killer whale over the full-year were mainly located on the west coast of Guadeloupe, where the majority of observations were made. The presence probability was also high north of Guadeloupe and northeast of Martinique. These areas of favorable habitat were supported by a consensus between models, with a variation coefficient lower than 0.04. Outside of these small areas, the predictions between models were quite variable, reaching a variation coefficient of 0.16 farthest east of the study area and to the south (see Fig 3).

Favorable habitats for the pantropical spotted dolphin over the full-year were almost exclusively located west of the Caribbean arc, with the highest presence probability along the coasts of Guadeloupe and Martinique. The models predicted a favorable habitat along the west coasts of Dominica and St. Lucia, reflecting similar environmental conditions to those in the observation areas. These results were supported by a variation coefficient lower than 0.05 in these areas (see Fig 4).

Favorable habitats for the Fraser's dolphin over the full-year was highly localized on the west coasts of Guadeloupe, Dominica and Martinique. The favorable habitat area was continuous between Dominica and Martinique, with a presence probability higher than 0.75, even though no sightings in Dominica were recorded in the dataset. These predictions reflected similar trophic conditions in terms of photosynthetic radiation and median and variable biomass of lower mesopelagic micronekton. These results were reinforced by coefficients of variation less than 0.1 and even 0.05 (see Fig 4).

Favorable habitats for the short-finned pilot whale over the full-year was close to the west coast of Guadeloupe up to that of Martinique, following the same continuity as for Fraser's dolphin. This result was supported by a variation coefficient lower than 0.03. In areas farther from the coasts, on the eastern front of the arc and south of the study area as well as near the smaller islands of the North, the presence probability was often higher than 0.6, providing a more diffuse map than that of other species. The variation coefficient lower than 0.06 indicates that these results remained reliable (see Fig 4).

Finally, favorable habitats for the humpback whale during the dry season was located in the immediate vicinity of the coasts and on shallow banks between and surrounding the islands. Although no observations were made near the islands between Saint-Martin and Guadeloupe, the model predicted a presence probability higher than 0.75 because the combination of depth and variation of surface water height was similar to where the species was observed. These results were supported by a low coefficient of variation. At higher depths or more variable surface water height to the south and east of the study area, the models showed

Figure 3. Habitat favorability maps of the sperm whale (*P. macrocephalus*), the bottlenose dolphin (*T. truncatus*), and the false killer whale (*P. crassidens*) over the full-year, according to the weighted average of model predictions associated with their coefficient of variation (CV).

little consensus (see Fig 4).

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Seasonal distribution trends

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For the sperm whale and the pantropical spotted dolphin, none of the explanatory variables were shared between the dry and the wet seasons (see Table 3). For the bottlenose dolphin, depth and median photosynthetic radiation variables (*par_med*) were selected in both seasons, with almost same contributions (see Table 3). For the false killer whale and the Fraser's dolphin, only the median of the highly migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton biomass (*lowhm_med*) was common between the models for the full-year and the dry season. Finally, for the short-finned pilot whale, the standard deviation of the migratory upper mesopelagic micronekton biomass (*uppm_sd*) was also common (see Table 3).

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Favorable habitats for the sperm whale and the pantropical spotted dolphin were more restricted in the wet season than in the dry season (see Fig 5). These remained mostly confined to the west coasts of Guadeloupe

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Figure 4. Habitat favorability maps of the pantropical spotted dolphin (*S. attenuata*), Fraser's dolphin (*L. hosei*), and the short-finned pilot whale (*G. macrorhynchus*) over the full-year, as well as that of the humpback whale (*M. novaeangliae*) over the dry season, according to the weighted average of model predictions associated with their coefficient of variation (CV).

for both species and Martinique for the pantropical spotted dolphin in the wet season, while extended to the west coasts of the three largest islands in the dry season and even to the west of Saint Kitts and Montserrat (see Fig 5). The opposite was observed for the bottlenose dolphin: predicted favorable habitats expanded further in the wet season than in the dry season, when they kept restricted to the immediate vicinity of the coasts (see Fig 5). These results were supported by coefficients of variation lower than 0.1 for the sperm whale and the pantropical spotted dolphin and even lower than 0.05 for the predicted favorable habitats of bottlenose dolphin. For species for which the wet season modeling was not performed, the maps obtained for the full-year and for the dry season were roughly equivalent (see Fig 6). For the Fraser's dolphin, the distribution seemed more extended on the west front of the Caribbean arc over the full-year. The predictions of favorable habitat were supported by coefficients of variation less than 0.1 for the Fraser's dolphin and 0.04 for the false killer whale and the short-finned pilot whale (see Fig 6).

Figure 5. Comparison of favorable habitat between the dry and the wet seasons for the sperm whale (*P. macrocephalus*), the bottlenose dolphin (*T. truncatus*), and the pantropical spotted dolphin (*S. attenuata*).

Figure 6. Comparison of favorable habitat between the full-year and the dry season for the false killer whale (*P. crassidens*), Fraser’s dolphin (*L. hosei*), and the short-finned pilot whale (*G. macrorhynchus*).

Discussion

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Methodological considerations

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The modeling process used in this study has been optimized to integrate state-of-the-art computational methods with a complex and heterogeneous dataset. However, there is still room for improvement.

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Data heterogeneity

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The inherent spatial sampling bias in the data was accounted for and corrected by sampling pseudo-absences within the surveyed area. This strategy, which mimics the sampling effort of observations to generate pseudo-absences, is well-established in the literature and is widely accepted for addressing sampling bias (Botella et al., 2020; Kéry et al., 2010; Phillips et al., 2009). The heterogeneity of observation methods was taken into account by assigning different weights to grid cells during the sampling of pseudo-absences. However, the

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data were also heterogeneous based on their sources, including standardized surveys, punctual studies and opportunistic data. Greater weights were assigned to presence data from surveys with dedicated efforts compared to data from opportunistic sightings and punctual studies. A higher weight might have been attributed to punctual studies, which are considered more reliable due to targeted research. Building one model per data source and integrating the outcome into a final single model could also be considered (see Point Process Models, Isaac et al. (2020)).

Modification of biomass variables

Modifying the median biomass of the highly migratory and non-migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton (lowhm_med and low_med) with the value 0 could lead to the construction of false response curves in the range where there is no data between 0 and the minimum value of the variable. On the favorable habitat maps, this discontinuity resulted in a lack of consensus among models in areas where the value was zero. It is probable that this modification enabled these variables to be retained on the basis of correlation criteria, whereas they could have been correlated with other variables relating to the presence of prey without modification. This method had been used in a study on deep divers, which are very often absent from areas where these variables were equal to 0 (Virgili, Hedon, et al., 2021). Although the model results are in line with known literature for some species (Wang et al., 2012), it would be preferable to prioritize the use of continuous variables such as sea surface height and eddy kinetic energy, which account for prey aggregation at the surface and throughout the water column (Green et al., 2020; Virgili, Hedon, et al., 2021).

Study of seasonality

For a more detailed analysis of seasonal dynamics, models could be built using monthly variables. For example, for humpback whales that arrive in the Sanctuary for calving in January (Réserve Naturelle de Saint Martin, 2019), it would be interesting to test the effect of the eddy kinetic energy (calculated from sea water velocities) or temperature at monthly resolution. This more precise study is motivated by the work of Meynecke et al. (2021), which suggests that whales choose calm and warm water conditions for the development of their calves.

Prediction quality

Favorable habitat maps were generated from ensemble models constructed using models selected based on a performance threshold (TSS > 0.7). The predictive quality of the models could be improved by generating a wide pool of predictors followed by an automatic selection of optimal predictor combinations with high predictive performance, as done in (Effrosynidis et al., 2020). However, this automated phase may lead to a decrease in the explanatory quality of the model, more from an ecological perspective than a statistical one. Additionally, performance can potentially increase with the inclusion of possible interactions between environmental variables. This particularly applies to models built using methods that are unable to detect interactions automatically (GLM, GAM, FDA, and MARS methods).

Extrapolation of predictions

To extrapolate predictions of individual density or favorable habitat, it is recommended that at least 30% of the study area be sampled (Buckland et al., 1993). In this study, 15,754 cells were surveyed at least once from December 2007 to November 2022 out of 51,108 cells for the entire study area, i.e. 31%. However, marine mammal sightings are rare. At most, 0.96% of the study area cells were presence cells for humpback whales during the dry season. To counterbalance this low percentage and obtain information on variables explaining species presence, pseudo-absences were sampled to cover 10% of the surveyed area, following Barbet-Massin et al. (2012). Furthermore, to reduce bias associated with non-surveyed areas, environmental variables were chosen based on their ecological relevance (Harris et al., 2013). Finally, all interpretations of

favorable habitat maps were conducted considering the coefficient of variation between models, as advised in Guillaumot et al. (2020).

Favorable habitats for marine mammals in the study area

The favorable habitat maps obtained for the study area, encompassing Anguilla to Saint Lucia and including the Agoa Sanctuary, represent an important milestone for the management of the marine protected area. These findings are innovative, particularly for understudied species such as the pantropical spotted dolphin, the Fraser’s dolphin, and the false killer whale.

Overall distribution

The results of species distribution modeling have unanimously shown that the most favorable habitats were located on the western coasts of the islands, known as lee-ward coasts because they face the Caribbean Sea rather than the Atlantic Ocean. The presence of sperm whales on the leeward coasts and their absence on the windward coasts had already been mentioned by Vachon (2022). For the pantropical spotted dolphin, a photo-identification study by Courtin et al. (2023) indicated that the populations in Martinique were smaller and more localized near the coasts compared to Guadeloupe. The obtained distribution maps reflected this nuance.

For most species, depth was a structuring variable in the distribution. This result was expected based on the literature (Mannocci et al., 2017). In the Bay of Biscay, the peak density of sperm whales was found at depths of 2000 meters (Virgili, Hedon, et al., 2021) and in Madeira, they were present at depths beyond 1000 meters (Fernandez et al., 2021). In the Balearic Islands, the species was preferentially found at depths between 2000 and 2500 meters but was also present between 500 and 1000 meter (Pirota et al., 2011). In the study area, the observation peak for sperm whales was located at depths close to 1000 meters, and the probability of presence was high between 700 and 2000 meters, which in line with most studies (see Fig 7). Depth was the most explanatory variable for bottlenose dolphin. This result is in line with those of Fernandez et al. (2021), who also revealed a maximum contribution of this variable for this species, compared with sperm whales, pilot whales and other dolphin species. The work of Lacey et al. (2022) also demonstrated a strong effect of depth and distance to the 50-meter isobath on the presence of bottlenose dolphins, supporting the results obtained in this study (see Fig 7). In Madeira, the pilot whale was predominantly found between 1000 and 2000 meters depth (Fernandez et al., 2021), which further corroborates the findings of our study (see Fig 7). For the humpback whale, the probability of presence increases as the zones become shallower, starting from depths of 1000m (see Fig 7). This result was in line with that of Meynecke et al. (2021), which indicated that whales preferred shallow areas during the reproduction period.

Dry and wet season distributions

Pirota et al. (2011) demonstrated in the Balearic Islands that sperm whale distribution differed based on their feeding or socializing activities. For instance, large males hunt alone in deep areas, while the groups formed by females and young individuals select hunting areas with cooler water temperatures. In the study area, mature males are only present for short stays during the dry season for breeding (Gero et al., 2014). Therefore, their presence would lead to more frequent observations of sperm whales in deep areas during the dry season compared to the wet season, which could explain the differences in distribution observed on the maps of favorable habitats, as also indicated by the explanatory variables.

For the bottlenose dolphin, research conducted in Guadeloupe revealed the existence of two morphotypes (Haderlé, 2022). The coastal or “Florida” morphotype was predominantly found at depths of 4 to 40 meters,

Figure 7. Response curves for the depth variable for all species except the pseudorca (variable with a contribution of less than 10%) in the full-year (FY) and for the humpback whale in the dry season (DS).

while the "white back" morphotype occurred at depths between 50 and 500 meters, and even up to 1000 meters. This morphotype, characterized by a larger body size and darker coloration, may correspond to the pelagic ecotype (Coché, 2019). Two eco-types have been identified based on genetic and morphological criteria in the Atlantic and North Pacific Oceans (Haderlé, 2022). Genetic studies on individuals in the Agoa Sanctuary should help clarify the definition of these ecotypes. Based on our study, it appears that the "pelagic" morphotype was more frequently observed during the wet season, while the coastal morphotype was more commonly observed during the dry season. This result is supported by a photo-identification study of the coastal morphotype, which indicated that 71% of individuals were observed between January and May, corresponding to the dry season (Coché, 2019). In the temperate zone, in the Bay of Biscay, seasonal distribution differences have also been observed, with pelagic individuals showing higher abundance offshore during winter (Laran, Authier, Blanck, et al., 2017).

The study of (Díaz-Torres et al., 2022) provided a number of insights into the seasonal distribution of pantropical spotted dolphins in Mexican waters of the Pacific Ocean. During the dry season, individuals were closer to the coast, where chlorophyll concentration was higher. The median biomass of highly migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton contributed 46% during the dry season, compared to only 6% during the wet season. In the wet season, variations in biomass of migrant lower mesopelagic micronekton primarily explained the distribution, with a contribution of 29%, which is still lower than the biomass contribution in the dry season. Biomass, like chlorophyll-a, is a trophic variable indicating the presence of prey. Thus, as in (Díaz-Torres et al., 2022), these elements showed that the distribution would be linked to seasonal changes in the ecosystem's productivity.

Distribution in the full-year and the dry season

For species for which there was insufficient data to build wet-season models, the full-year and dry season models resulted in the construction of similar favorable habitat maps. This could be explained either by the limited number of data points in the wet season compared to the dry season or because the distribution in the wet season was similar to that in the dry season. For the false killer whale and the short-finned pilot whale, respectively 17% and 31% of the data were associated with the wet season only, and the distribution of presence points was similar for both seasons. For the short-finned pilot whale, a study in Martinique indicated no seasonality (De Montgolfier et al., 2019). Thus, for these two species, the similarities between the models obtained for the full-year and the dry season can be explained by the similarities in the data collected during both seasons. For the Fraser's dolphin, 15% of the data were associated with the wet season only. The distribution of presence points showed that sightings during the wet season were all close to the coast, while a few sightings during the dry season were further offshore (4 out of 79 sightings). Therefore, the similarities between the models obtained for the full-year and the dry season could be explained by the low contribution of wet season sightings.

Perspectives

Acquiring more observation data

Acoustic data could also contribute to the interpretation of favorable habitat maps. Frasier et al. (2021) demonstrated that models incorporating both visual and acoustic data outperformed models based solely on visual sightings. Acoustic detections of sperm whales were located within predicted favorable habitat areas. Considering that the detection range of sperm whale clicks is relatively limited, ranging from 4 to 20 km (Cauchy et al., 2020), these detections confirmed the presence of sperm whales in the predicted zones. For the humpback whale, whose song has a range of up to 100 km (Kowarski et al., 2022), multiple acoustic detections around Martinique and to the west of the island chain from Anguilla to Saint Kitts suggested a significant

presence of this species near these islands. Therefore, it could be relevant to maintain this detection method as a complement to the visual method.

The data provided by the Agoa Sanctuary were mostly collected within the marine protected area. The favorable habitat maps indicated a high probability of presence around the islands in the study area. Thus, it is essential to establish links between favorable habitat maps and data collected on islands outside the administrative boundaries of the Agoa Sanctuary. These maps fuel the international collaboration efforts being developed by the Agoa Sanctuary with neighboring territories and provide a valuable tool to identify areas of interest that could be prioritized for data acquisition through a common programme.

Understanding the effect of anthropogenic variables

Several studies have highlighted negative influence of anthropogenic activities on marine mammals, such as maritime traffic, which can lead to collisions, noise disturbances, and disturbance from whale-watching activities, particularly when practiced by recreational boaters (Coché, 2020; Farmer et al., 2022; Ratel et al., 2021). Visualization of the maritime traffic variable, calculated based on vessel passage time, speed, and quantity, showed that the major shipping routes run along the western coasts of Martinique to Guadeloupe, where the probability of presence for all studied species was the highest. More specifically, a study in Guadeloupe showed that the six species studied (no information for the pseudorca) were all threatened by the vessel speed, but also by the frequency of passages for dolphins (Madon et al., 2022). Coché (2020) demonstrated that the maritime traffic is a source of disturbance for resident species in these areas, particularly for sperm whales, which are more frequently observed during periods of lower traffic density. Therefore, it would be valuable to assess the favorable habitat maps in relation to a mapping of these different human activities. This analysis would provide insights for the implementation of potential new protection measures.

Conducting additional analyses

The favorable habitat maps were constructed based on statistical correlations between presence / pseudo-absence data and environmental variables. Therefore, they do not explicitly capture certain ecological processes that may explain species presence, such as biotic interactions, ecophysiological parameters, or population social structure. For example, predation and competition can reduce the predicted favorable habitat areas (Lambert, Virgili, et al., 2017). A study on vocal clans of sperm whales revealed that the species distribution is also influenced by population structure and cultural information transmitted among individuals, rather than environmental variables solely (Vachon et al., 2022). This type of study is more closely related to the mechanisms explaining species presence, as opposed to purely correlational statistical relationships (Dormann, Elith, et al., 2013; Evans et al., 2015).

The study was conducted independently on the seven most frequently observed cetacean species in the study area. A multi-species modeling approach, known as Joint Species Distribution Model, would allow for the integration of multiple species from a community into a common model, including rare species. This could improve predictive performance, the ability to detect species interactions (Pollock et al., 2014; Warton et al., 2015), and the production of distribution maps for less frequently observed species, with their distribution partially informed by the distribution of more common species (Erickson and Smith, 2022; Zhang et al., 2020). The distribution of rare species could also be studied using bivariate models, involving a single predictor and combined in an ensemble model (Breiner et al., 2015).

Take-home message

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This research combined data from different sources to build distribution maps of cetaceans in the Eastern Caribbean (French West Indies), serving as a preliminary management resource for the marine protected area of the Agoa Sanctuary. For all species, the most favorable habitats were found along the leeward coasts, west of the islands. Depth, biomass of highly migratory lower mesopelagic micronekton, photosynthetic radiation, and variation in sea surface height were consistently identified as the most explanatory variables. The Agoa Sanctuary relies on scientific knowledge of the species ecology to derive the most appropriate management measures, with regard to human activities. This study will therefore directly inform the Sanctuary's management plan and measures could be modulated according to the season for certain species. The maps will be an excellent visual tool for discussions with all those involved in the maritime sector (e.g. major ports) and for drafting technical advice. They can also be compared with maps of anthropogenic pressures faced by cetaceans, particularly maritime traffic and whale-watching activity. The methodology established in this study could provide valuable insights for comparable initiatives. Finally, to improve this study, to expand the database beyond the administrative boundaries of the Agoa Sanctuary, international collaborations with other islands in the Caribbean arc are encouraged.

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Conflict of interest disclosure

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The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

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Data, script, code, and supplementary information availability

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Data, script and codes are available online: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10844839> (Maalouf and Hugon, 2024). Supplementary information is also available online : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10844839> (Maalouf and Hugon, 2024).

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